

Tardigrade (COI)
Acutuncus antarcticus

Mite (COI)
Alaskozetes antarcticus

Mite (COI)
Halozetes spp.

Mite (COI)
Stereotydeus spp.

Springtail (COI)
Cryptopygus spp.

Springtail (COI)
Friesea spp.

Springtail (COI)
Gomphiocephalus spp.

Angiosperm (ITS1)
Colobanthus quitensis

9e-05

Angiosperm (ITS1)
Deschampsia antarctica

Moss (ITS1)
Bryum argenteum

Haplotype
■ C1
■ C2

Moss (ITS1)
Schistidium antarctici

Lichen (ITS1)
Umbilicaria spp.

Lichen (ITS1)
Usnea spp.

